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Need Structure among Distance Mode Learners in Context of Some Social Correlates

*Dr. Dinesh Kumar**

The present study was conducted on 100 undergraduate respondents belonging to Distance Education of Patna town. They were selected on the basis of incidental-cum-purposive sampling technique. The objectives of the study were to examine the influence of inhabitation, parental involvement, parental education and SES on need for achievement and level of aspiration among the respondents. It was hypothesized that - There would be significant influence of (i) urban-rural inhabitation, (ii) parental involvement, (iii) parental education, and (iv) SES on need for achievement and level of aspiration of the respondents. For the purpose, Mukherjee's Need for Achievement Scale, Singh's Level of Aspiration Scale, Akhtar's Parental Involvement Scale, Bhardwaj's SES Scale were used to measure need for achievement, level of aspiration, parental involvement and SES of distant mode learners. Besides these, a PDS was used to get other necessary informations about the respondents. The scales were employed and data were obtained as per directions in the manuals of the scales. The obtained data were treated using t-test. The results confirmed all the formulated hypotheses. It was concluded that inhabitation, parental involvement, parental education and SES all are conducive to motivational correlates (need structure) under reference.

Introduction

The present study embodies some components. The first component is distance mode of education which refers to an educational system characterized by various modes such as self instructed printed materials, audio video aids, Telly conferencing system. Emailing etc which provides education to the people even they are sitting at home. The system imparts education through various modes and technologies mentioned above. The second component is need for achievement which refers to the tendency of striving success or attainment of the desired goal. Peter Stratton and Nickey Hayes (2017) defined it as the motivation to accomplish valued goals and to avoid failure. The level of aspiration, the third important component of the present study, is an individual goal or expectation in regard to this goodness of his own future setting behaviour which occurs within the range of difficulty of the individuals. Chaplin (1985) defined it as a self imposed standard against which a person judges his own performance. Level of aspiration varies with the pattern of success or failure.

The importance and significant of distance education can be viewed from diverse angles. The growing population of the country demand a system of education which can bring learning to the door steps. The conventional system of education fails to provides education to those who live in the remote areas of the country. It also fails to provide socially and economically backward. Such people can be very much benefited by the distance educational system. It is the system of education which helps people to achieve higher education without any formality for attending regular classes unlike conventional system of education. The University which impoarts distance learning is known as open university which can simply be considered as university without wall.

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Open system of education has become a necessity in the present time. In view of a number of barriers created by formal conventional system of education. The conventional type of education indeed has created several barriers which debar those people from taking education who cannot afford to come to college and the university for higher education because of several reasons including regional remoteness, economic backwardness, social disadvantaged, engagement in various trades and the like. The distance educational system indeed a boon in disguised for such people and hence it is an urgent need of the time to promote distance education as far as practicable.

Objectives

The present study intends to examine the influence of (i) inhabitation, (ii) parental involvement, (iii) parental education and (iv) SES on need for achievement and level of aspiration.

Hypotheses

It was hypothesized that there would be significant influence of (i) urban - rural inhabitation, (ii) high and low parental involvement, (iii) high and low level of parental education and (iv) high and low SES groups of distant learners on their need for achievement and level of aspiration.

Method of Study

Sample

A sample of 160 undergraduate respondents were selected from NOU study Centre, Biscomaun Bhawan, Gandhi Maidan, Patna using purposive sampling. They were equal in respect of urban (N = 50), rural (N = 50), high (N = 50) and low (N = 50) parental involvement groups, high (N = 50) and low (N = 50) parental education groups and high (N = 50) and low (N = 50) parental SES groups respectively. Other than these conditions they were matched so far as practicable.

Research Tools

- (1) A PDS was used to get the essential information about the respondents.
- (2) Akhtar's Parental Participation Scale was used to measure parental participation of the respondents.
- (3) Mukherjee's Need for Achievement Scale was used to measure need for achievement of the respondents.
- (4) Singh's Level of Aspiration Scale was used to measure the level of aspiration of the respondents belonging to distant modes of education.
- (5) Bhardwaj's SES Scale was used to measure SES of the respondents.

Procedure

Scale along with PDS were employed on 300 respondents and data were obtained as per direction of the manual concerned. Using median cut high and low groups were formed in respect of parental education, SES and parental participation. Finally, 200 respondents were selected equal in respect of urban-rural inhabitation, parental participation non-participation, high and low parental education and high and low SES respectively.

Results

Table-01

t-ratio showing the effect of urban / rural inhabitation on need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents of distance mode learning.

Inhabitation							
Dimensions	Urban (N=50)		Rural (N=50)		t-ratio	df	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			

Need for Achievement	35.40	5.77	24.38	6.68	9.57	98	<.01
Level of Aspiration	20.78	4.07	14.47	4.40	7.42	98	<.01

The results displayed in table-01 clearly showed the superiority of urban respondents in respect of need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents belonging to distance learners (Need for achievement : $t = 9.57$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$; Level of Aspiration : $t = 7.42$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$). Thus, first hypothesis is retained. This findings is interpreted on the ground of facilities availed by urban respondents as compared to rural respondents leading to higher level of need for achievement and level of aspiration.

Table-02

t-ratio showing the effect of parental participation of need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents of distance education.

Parental Participation							
Dimensions	High (N=50)		Low (N=50)		t-ratio	df	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Need for Achievement	38.46	4.98	30.33	5.11	8.13	98	<.01
Level of Aspiration	20.56	3.12	14.78	3.45	8.76	98	<.01

The results displayed in table-02 clearly indicated the superiority of respondents belonging to high parental participation group than their counterparts belonging to low parental participation group in respect of need for achievement and level of aspiration (Need for achievement : $t = 8.13$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$); Level of aspiration $t = 8.76$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$). Thus, the second hypothesis is retained. This finding is interpreted on the ground of sincerity, attentiveness of parental involvement in the activities of their wards than those respondents whose parents are not involved leading to have higher need for achievement and level of aspiration in superior group than inferior group.

Table-03

t-ratio showing the effect of parental education on need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents belonging to distance mode of education.

Parental Education							
Dimensions	High (N=50)		Low (N=50)		t-ratio	df	p
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Need for Achievement	37.45	3.67	30.31	3.84	9.52	98	<.01
Level of Aspiration	19.70	4.69	13.06	4.76	7.06	98	<.01

the result displayed in table-03 clearly indicated the significant effect of parental education on motivational correlates of the respondents under reference. The respondents belonging to high parental education group dominated in respect of need for achievement and level of aspiration as compared to their counterparts belonging to low parental education group of respondents. (Need for achievement : $t = 9.52$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$); Level of aspiration : $t = 7.06$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$). Thus, third hypothesis also is retained. This findings might be interpreted on the ground that highly educated persons are very much sincere and devoted to the achievement and related matters. Such people are fully aware about the over all development of their wards as compared to their counterparts.

Table-04

t-ratio showing the effect of SES on need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents of distance mode of education.

Dimensions	SES				t-ratio	df	p
	High (N=50)		Low (N=50)				
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Need for Achievement	39.52	5.11	30.96	5.26	8.31	98	<.01
Level of Aspiration	20.87	3.88	13.95	3.96	8.87	98	<.01

The results displayed in table-04 clearly indicated the significant effect of SES on need for achievement and level of aspiration of respondents. (Need for achievement : $t = 8.31$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$); Level of Aspiration : $t = 8.87$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$). High SES group of respondents dominated in respect of need for achievement and level of aspiration. Thus, fourth hypothesis is also retained. This finding is interpreted on the ground of facilitating conditions and opportunity of getting almost every kind of needs due to privileged socio-economic conditions leading to have higher need for achievement and level of aspiration in such respondents than their counterparts belonging to low socio-economic conditions.

Conclusions

Need for achievement and level of aspiration are attributed by (i) urban inhabitation, (ii) high parental participation, (iii) higher level of parental education and (iv) high SES group of respondents.

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